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EFFECTS OF PESTICIDES ON *Melipona quadrifasciata anthidioides* (MANDACAIA BEE)

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Abstract

Bees are insects of recognized importance for maintaining biodiversity and agricultural production. They represent around 70% of biotic pollinating agents^[1] and are responsible for the pollination of approximately 80% of plants used in human food^[2]. However, excessive use and the increasing release of pesticides represent a serious threat to bees^[3]. In this sense, the objective of this study was to evaluate the toxicity of three active ingredients: triflumizole, lambda-cyhalothrin and fenpyroximate in *Melipona quadrifasciata anthidioides*. Bees were exposed to different doses and concentrations of a.i. through three routes of exposure (ingestion, topical and surface contact), according to protocols established by the OECD and similar studies^[4,5,6,7]. The survival

and behavioral variations of bees were evaluated at time intervals of 1, 6, 12, 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours, after exposure. Survival data were subjected to the Log-Rank test, using Software R^[8]. The results showed high toxicity of lambda-cyhalothrin, causing a significant lethal effect via topical ($p < 0.01$) and ingestion ($p < 0.01$). In contact surface exposure, lambda-cyhalothrin did not cause a significant lethal effect ($p > 0.05$), however, it caused paralysis and difficulty in locomotion in the first 24 hours. Triflumizole and fenpyroximate did not cause a significant lethal effect ($p > 0.05$), but affected the behavior of bees, causing disorientation, difficulty in locomotion, agitation, paralysis and prostration, in the three routes of exposure, in addition to reducing food consumption. on exposure through ingestion. In this study, lambda-cyhalothrin was highly toxic to *M. quadrifasciata anthidioides*, causing a significant lethal effect and evident behavioral changes. Triflumizole and fenpyroximate did not present lethal toxicity, but affected the behavior of bees, which may represent a risk to the survival and development of colonies.

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